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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

The past decade has seen a revolution in the field of radio transients. Fast Radio Bursts "exploded" on the scene and represent one of the most interesting puzzles in astrophysics today. The CHIME Fast Radio Burst project has recently emerged as a world-leader in the field, offering potential for determining the nature of these objects and for realizing their potential as novel cosmic probes. Meanwhile, the area of "slow" radio transients, traditionally associated with accreting sources and associated jets, is also undergoing a renaissance as part of advances in time-domain and multi-messenger astrophysics, the latter thanks to aLIGO/Virgo. This white paper will review the key science questions to be addressed by observations of FRBs and radio transients, and map the relevant observational requirements onto new and envisioned future radio telescopes and instruments, including CHIME, CHIME/FRB, CHIME/Outriggers, CHORD, JVLA, SKA, and ngVLA.

Lead author and affiliation	Victoria Kaspi (Dept of Physics & McGill Space Institute, McGill University)
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Email address of lead author	vkaspi@physics.mcgill.ca
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Other authors and affiliations

J. J. Ruan (MSI/McGill U.), G. Sivakoff (U. Alberta), P. Boyle (MSI/McGill U.), J. Brown (U. Calgary), M. Dobbs (MSI/McGill U.), M. Drout (Dunlap Institute/UofT), E. Fonseca (MSI/McGill U.), D. Haggard (MSI/McGill U.), K. Masui (MIT), A. Naidu (MSI/McGill U.), C. Ng (Dunlap Institute), U. Pen (CITA/UofT), P. Scholz (Dunlap Institute/UofT), J. Sievers (MSI/McGill U.), K. Smith (Perimeter), I. Stairs (UBC), K. Vanderlinde (Dunlap Institute/UofT)

1 Introduction

The field of radio transients encompasses phenomena involving sources that are extremely variable and/or only temporarily observable. The field has, in the past decade, undergone a revolution, particularly at the short timescale end (under approximately 1 s), thanks to an increase in compute power, data storage relative to cost, and telescopes with large mapping speeds. Meanwhile, large-scale radio surveys, driven by developments in time-domain astronomy, notably in high-cadence optical observations, have also enabled a renaissance in radio transient science on the days to weeks time scale. The direct detection of gravitational waves by Advanced LIGO/Virgo and the blossoming of multi-messenger astrophysics with the discovery of the first double neutron-star (DNS) merger GW170817 have enabled observations of merger aftermaths and their associated radio emission. The latter is transient on time scales of weeks to months. Though many radio sources are variable, we focus here on relatively short transients – Fast Radio Bursts (FRBs) – as well as slower transients involving stellar-mass compact objects and their ephemeral radio jets. We omit radio pulsars whose emission is ever-present even if observable only a small fraction of the time (but see WPs by E. Fonseca and I. Stairs on this subject). Similarly we omit AGN and blazars which, though exhibiting dramatic variability, are still, for our purposes, non-ephemeral sources.

FRBs are a recently discovered (Lorimer et al., 2007) phenomenon consisting of few-ms bursts of radio waves having dispersion measures (DMs) indicating an extragalactic origin (see Cordes & Chatterjee, 2019; Petroff et al., 2019, for recent reviews). Their nature is presently unknown. Some FRB DMs suggest cosmological distances, and this has been confirmed in three sources thus far (Tendulkar et al., 2017; Bannister et al., 2019; Ravi et al., 2019). FRBs are therefore believed to have enormous radio luminosities, upwards of 10^{42} erg s⁻¹, indicating a powerful engine (though GRB luminosities are generally several orders magnitude larger). Moreover, FRBs are ubiquitous, with observed all-sky rates of ~ 1000 per day (e.g. Lawrence et al., 2017).

Of the presently published ~ 80 FRBs¹, 11 are known to exhibit repeat bursts (Spitler et al., 2016; CHIME/FRB Collaboration et al., 2019a,b; Bannister et al., 2019). There are many models for FRBs (see Platts et al., 2018, for a recent compilation); these range from merging neutron stars (at odds with repetition and the observed rate) to cosmic-string cusps. FRBs may yet prove to consist of multiple different classes of source. FRBs have also drawn great interest because of their potential as cosmic probes. Unlike, for example, gamma-ray bursts (GRBs), FRBs have imprinted on their detected signal precious information about their path to us. Specifically, the DM is the total electron column depth along the line of sight, the rotation measure (RM) is a combination of the sight-line magnetic field and electron density, and the scattering measure (SM) is sensitive to electron density inhomogeneities along the path. Therefore the potential detection of a large number of FRBs together with their cosmological distances suggests FRBs can be novel tools to probe the structure and evolution of the Universe.

Radio sources that are transient (or highly variable) on timescales greater than ~ 1 sec (“slow” radio transients) can probe extreme physics in the Universe, including the generation of GRBs and relativistic jets, and space-time in extreme gravity (e.g. Miller-Jones et al., 2019). Although relativistic jets have been known for decades, critical jet properties are still unconstrained. How jets are launched, as well as the connection between such outflows (typically observed at radio frequencies)¹ and the accretion inflows (typically observed with X-rays) that ultimately power them, are still poorly understood. Outbursts of the radio transients that arise from accreting stellar-mass compact objects permit studies on observable time scales that can inform on the far longer timescale evolution seen in accreting supermassive black holes (relevant to galactic-scale feedback of baryons and energy McNamara et al., 2009). Slow radio transients also constrain our understanding of the cycles of baryon and energy feedback (e.g., through outflows and supernovae) on more local scales. Recent multi-wavelength studies of the interaction from GW170817 (e.g., Ruan et al., 2018) with its local environment (see below) are one example of how radio observations trace ejecta interactions with the interstellar medium. Radio observations of supernovae over both long and short timescales (e.g., SN 1986J and SN2013ge; Bietenholz & Bartel, 2017; Drout et al., 2016) also probe the shock interaction with the circumstellar medium—thereby providing novel constraints on the progenitor systems and evolutionary history of explosive transients. Finally, Canadian radio astronomers are beginning to participate in or lead wide-field radio surveys (e.g., the Very Large Array Sky Survey and daily monitoring of the sky with CHIME), hence are poised to make strides in time-domain astrophysics such as extreme scattering events,

¹see frbcat.org

flare stars, tidal disruption events, and likely, novel phenomena.

The recent detection of GW170817 by aLIGO/Virgo (Abbott et al., 2017c) and its associated GRB (Abbott et al., 2017b) resulted in the first “multi-messenger” follow-up and identification of a host galaxy and a radio afterglow most likely associated with a relativistic jet. This afterglow has provided interesting information about the geometry of the DNS binary, the kilonova and the structure of jets, and possibly even aided in a new measurement of Hubble’s constant. If gravitational waves from DNS mergers become commonly observed, such radio afterglow observations could thus be very fruitful, enabling a new cottage industry in the study of jets, kilonovae, and possibly be new cosmological tools as “standard sirens.”

Next we list the main open questions for FRBs, slow transients and multi-messenger astrophysics, the main radio transients discussed in this white paper.

2 What are FRBs and Can they be Used as Cosmic Probes?

What are FRBs? Dozens of possible models currently attempt to explain FRBs. However, no current model can unambiguously explain all the observations, which include, but are not limited to, the observed burst brevity, luminosity, rate, source environments and propagation effects. Only three FRBs have been identified with host galaxies thus far: one dwarf and two ellipticals. This has opened more questions than it answered.

- Are FRBs young or old objects? Most models posit one or the other, with e.g. the magnetar model indicating young, while e.g. a DNS merger model arguing old. To answer this key question, additional FRB localizations are imperative to identify types of host galaxies, and where in those hosts the sources reside. Arcsecond localizations are required for all but the closest sources (Eftekhari & Berger, 2017). With host galaxies identified, sub-arcsecond localizations are important for deep optical/IR imaging to understand the location within the host galaxy and the properties of the FRB’s immediate environment.
- Do FRBs represent a single class of object? There may be a variety of cosmic sources producing FRB-like bursts. Currently we suspect at least two classes, repeating and non-repeating (but see below). Current hints of heterogeneity include a diversity of burst morphologies and radio frequency distributions (e.g. CHIME/FRB Collaboration et al., 2019b), a diversity of polarization properties, and a variety of scattering measures at the same excess DM (e.g. CHIME/FRB Collaboration et al., 2019c). The known host galaxies are also very different. Answering this question requires the detection and comparison of a large number of FRBs with arcsecond localizations.
- Are all FRBs repeaters? High sensitivity and regular monitoring of large sky areas, as performed by CHIME/FRB, are ideal for answering this question. If, for example, the number of events per source scales roughly with source exposure this would suggest repetition is generic. Similarly, follow-up of repeaters with large single-dish telescopes like Arecibo and FAST, as well as SKA1, will probe deep into the flux distribution, and could identify repeaters that large-field-of-view but less sensitive telescopes miss. Narrow field-of-view interferometers, given sufficient time, can detect repeater bursts and localize them (e.g. Chatterjee et al., 2017).
- What are FRB environments like? Knowing the properties of their environment will provide important clues to the nature of the sources. With localizations, host galaxy identifications are possible, as are searches for coincident sources such as star-forming regions. The DM, RM and SM provide clues too but must be disentangled from effects of propagation. This is enabled with FRB localizations, through the knowledge of the FRB surroundings.
- What is the emission mechanism for FRBs? Though multiple mechanisms could be at play, any emission model must explain the large luminosities and short durations, which suggest compact objects. For repeaters, repetition rates and lifetimes are important as they put strong constraints on energetics, which, at least for the highly prolific FRB 121102, provide key challenges to e.g. neutron-star models (see, e.g. Lyutikov, 2017). Understanding the emission mechanism is facilitated by detailed study of burst morphology, hence high time- and frequency-resolution data, good signal strength, and polarization sensitivity.

Can FRBs be used as novel cosmic probes?

- Can FRBs solve the ‘Missing Baryon’ problem? A long-standing problem in astrophysics is that Big Bang nucleosynthesis and properties of the CMB both measure a larger baryon density than has been yet found. Substantial evidence points to these “missing baryons” being located in the intergalactic medium (IGM) and in circumgalactic

media (CGM), i.e. haloes of galaxies. However until now, detecting these baryons has proven challenging since these media are both highly ionized. FRBs can enable major progress, as their DMs are sensitive to the free electron component of this plasma. McQuinn (2014) showed that DM distributions from 100-1000 FRBs can distinguish among different models for baryonic distributions in CGM. Cross-correlation with thermal Sunyaev-Zeldovich maps at the arcminute scale for $\sim 10^4$ FRBs could detect the warm/hot component of the IGM (Muñoz & Loeb, 2018). Knowing redshifts for these same sources along with those of intervening haloes can enable determination of the fractions of baryons in the IGM and CGM (e.g. Ravi, 2019; Prochaska & Zheng, 2019; Walters et al., 2019).

- Can FRBs constrain cosmology? FRBs have been shown to have potentially many interesting cosmological applications beyond the missing baryon problem. These include constraining the CMB optical depth using FRBs from the Epoch of Reionization (Fialkov & Loeb, 2016), testing Einstein’s Equivalence Principle (Wei et al., 2015), studying large-scale structure (e.g. Masui & Sigurdson, 2015) and breaking the degeneracy between optical depth of galaxies and clusters with the cosmological growth rate inferred from free electron peculiar velocities in the kinetic Sunyaev-Zeldovich (kSZ) effect (Madhavacheril et al., 2019). For these sorts of applications, generally large samples with redshifts out to large distances are required.

- Can FRBs teach us about cosmic magnetism? Magnetic fields display order up to at least the galaxy cluster scale (Ryu et al., 2012; Widrow et al., 2012). These fields likely grew through astrophysical dynamo processes from initial seed fields. The source of the seeds is unknown, but if primordial, could provide a new probe of the physics of the early Universe. Akahori et al. (2016) and Vazza et al. (2018) showed that a large sample of Faraday-rotated FRBs would offer a unique probe of large-scale magnetic fields, since the RM can be measured to high precision. If the FRBs are well localized, spatial information can be used to isolate contributions from fields outside the host galaxies and to study correlations as a function of spatial scale (Vernstrom et al., 2019). Order in magnetic fields on scales much larger than galaxy clusters is thought to be a smoking gun for a primordial origin.

- Can we detect gravitational lensing in FRBs? Muñoz et al. (2016) suggested FRBs can be observably gravitationally lensed by MACHOS having $20\text{--}100M_{\odot}$, a range otherwise poorly constrained, with the fraction of dark matter in such objects interestingly constrained by an absence of lenses in $\sim 10^4$ FRBs. Nanolensing of FRBs by low-mass compact objects has been argued to be detectable if such objects exist (Eichler, 2017). Precision measurements of H_0 may be possible using strongly lensed FRBs in the SKA era (Li et al., 2018). Detections of lensing require $10^4\text{--}10^5$ events, as well as high time and frequency resolution.

3 Open Questions on “Slow” Radio Transients

Although there are many open questions in the wider field of “slow” radio transients, here we list the main open questions being probed by Canadian astronomers.

- What are the properties of relativistic jets (and how do they evolve)? Although relativistic jets have been studied for decades, their main properties as observed in slow radio transients are poorly known. Although the basic Blandford & Königl (1979) model for relativistic jets posits that the jets are self-similar cones, there are few constraints on this shape. Since direct imaging of radio jets rarely resolves the transverse jet (c.f. Stirling et al., 2001), newer techniques that use fast radio timing (Tetarenko et al., 2019) can potentially probe jet geometry at multiple frequencies, and thus multiple locations down the axis of the jet, while simultaneously constraining jet speed. This requires simultaneous observations at a few to a few 10^3 ’s of GHz, with a preference for wider bandwidth facilities with sub-array capacities. The JVLA is useful for the brightest accreting stellar-mass black holes; however, higher sensitivity facilities like the ngVLA and SKA will be required to make real progress. Measuring the quasi-simultaneous (within ~ 1 day) broadband spectral energy distribution across most of the electromagnetic spectrum can also place constraints on jet physics (Russell et al., 2014). This requires strong multi-wavelength coordination. Facilities that have flexible scheduling (e.g., sub-array observing with SKA1-Mid or ngVLA) or naturally provide for daily monitoring (e.g., CHORD or DSA 2000) are critical.

- Are relativistic jets launched due to the spin of the accretor or the accretion disk? Since the energy in jets arises from accretion, these two processes are clearly connected. However, it remains unclear whether jets are launched due to the spin of an accretor or the accretion disk. High angular resolution imaging can determine when the

jet is launched, and connected to the accretion properties at that time (Miller-Jones et al., 2012). This requires access to facilities like the VLBA (although recent work with long-lived ejecta observed by MeerKAT suggests that the baselines of SKA1-Mid may be sufficient) and X-ray timing instruments. A second approach is to probe the luminosities of the relativistic jet and the accretion flow at multiple times in a radio outburst for many different accretors (e.g., van den Eijnden et al., 2018). Finally, the recent discovery that a fraction of tidal disruption events (TDEs) will produce relativistic jets (e.g. Sw J1644+57; Eftekhari et al., 2018) offers the promise of studying the both the jet launching and cessation processes as the accretion rate onto the super-massive black hole varies by order of magnitude over a period of years. Combined with measurements of black hole or neutron-star spin, facilities like the JVLA and SKA precursors are helpful; however, the higher sensitivity of the ngVLA or SKA1-Mid will be needed to study a large sample of accreting neutron stars and tidal disruption events.

- What are the explosion mechanisms and progenitor systems and of explosive transients? Radio emission from explosive transients such as (e.g. Finzell et al., 2018), supernovae (SNe; e.g., de Witt et al., 2016), and merging neutron stars (e.g., Dobie et al., 2018) originates from the interaction of the fastest ejecta ($v > 0.1c$) with the circumstellar medium. As a result, the radio emission traces both the presence of out-flows/jets and the mass loss history of the progenitor star in the years to centuries before explosion—a powerful constraint on the nature of the progenitor system. Recent results from radio monitoring of a wide variety of transients have revealed both that stars *other* than the progenitors of GRBs are capable of launching relativistic material at the time of their death (e.g. Soderberg et al., 2010), and that a wide range of massive stars undergo a period of enhanced mass-loss during in the years immediately preceding core-collapse, which is not predicted by models of stellar evolution (Yaron et al., 2017; Margutti et al., 2017a). However, both the fraction of stellar explosions that harbour central engines and the full range of stars which undergo this eruptive behaviour are unknown. Addressing these questions will require monitoring campaigns of a large number of objects, favouring facilities with broadband capabilities (often above a GHz). Facilities like the JVLA and SKA precursors continue to make progress; however, the higher sensitivity of the ngVLA or SKA1-Mid will be needed for a statistical samples of such interactions.

- What is the nature of the transient radio sky? It is likely that we are missing large numbers of SN, TDEs, and GRBs; the former two if they occur in regions of high optical extinction or are confused with AGN variability (as they are typically identified in optical surveys; Gal-Yam et al., 2006), and the latter as they are highly beamed with the inverse GRB beaming factor being poorly constrained (Piran et al., 2013). Blind imaging radio surveys like those currently conducted by the JVLA (the Very Large Array Sky Survey; Lacy et al., 2019) and those to be done by the SKA precursors (e.g., the ASKAP Variables and Slow Transients Survey; Murphy et al., 2013) will provide the first real constraints on the number of extragalactic radio transients in the first half of the next decade. CHIME’s and eventually CHORD’s daily mapping of the northern sky will also identify new classes of transients. Such blind surveys often lead to more questions, which may require deeper surveys with SKA-Mid 1 or ngVLA.

4 Open Questions on Multi-Messenger Radio Transient Observations

If gravitational waves from DNS mergers become commonly observed, radio afterglow observations could enable a new industry in the study of jets, kilonovae, and may be new cosmological tools as “standard sirens.” Here we list the main open questions on multi-messenger radio transients and describe observations needed to address them.

- Do all DNS mergers produce successful GRB jets? Radio and X-ray observations of the synchrotron afterglow of GW170817 showed a slow brightening over months (Haggard et al., 2017; Margutti et al., 2017b; Ruan et al., 2018; Nynka et al., 2018; Troja et al., 2019), which has been explained either as a highly relativistic jet viewed off-axis that successfully broke out of the surrounding ejecta, or as a relativistic jet choked by the surrounding ejecta and produced a “cocoon” having isotropic afterglow emission. The second scenario is also motivated by the faint and distinctive γ -ray emission from GW170817, and may constitute a new class of short GRBs (sGRBs). However, VLBI imaging resolved the superluminal motion of the jet (Mooley et al., 2018), thus proving that the jet broke out of the kilonova ejecta. Nevertheless, it may be that for some DNS mergers, the associated sGRB jets are choked. A simple test would be to observe the synchrotron afterglows of many mergers; if all launch jets, they will be pointed randomly, leading to a diversity in their synchrotron afterglows. If instead the jets are quenched by the kilonova

ejecta, their afterglows will be isotropic. Radio monitoring can be performed with the JVLA, CHORD and SKA, and VLBI imaging may resolve successful jets if the merger is close enough.

- What is the structure of GRB jets? Prior to GW170817, our standard picture of GRB jet angular structure has been a “top-hat” with a high Lorentz factor within the jet opening angle, and no outflow outside the jet opening angle (e.g., van Eerten et al., 2010; van Eerten & MacFadyen, 2011). Hydrodynamic simulations of GRB jets have long predicted that interactions between the jet and circumburst gas will produce a ‘structured’ jet with Lorentz factor that decreases away from the jet centre (Xie et al., 2018; Lazzati et al., 2018). To confirm this, we need to observe a relatively off-axis jet, which may not produce a bright sGRB. The off-axis jet produced in GW170817 provided a probe of the structure of sGRB jets for the first time. Radio and X-ray observations of the afterglow of GW170817 displayed a slow rise indicative of a structured jet (Margutti et al., 2018; Alexander et al., 2018; Troja et al., 2019). Since sGRB jets are narrow ($\sim 10^\circ$), the majority of sGRB jets from DNS mergers detected by aLIGO/Virgo will be off-axis, so radio monitoring (preferable to X-rays, since we can achieve deeper and denser light curve sampling) of more sGRB afterglows can provide probes of the diversity of sGRB jet structure, and how they relate to the properties of the merging binary.

- Is there a synchrotron afterglow from the kilonova ejecta? Aside from the jet afterglow, the kilonova ejecta itself can produce an afterglow (Nakar & Piran, 2011; Hotokezaka et al., 2018). The ejecta is thought to have velocities of $0.1-0.3c$ depending on their exact origin, and will also shock the surrounding interstellar medium. This ejecta afterglow is fainter and peaks much later (on timescales of years post-merger) than the jet afterglow, due to its lower velocity. In GW170817, deep radio and X-ray observations have not yet detected an ejecta afterglow ~ 3 yr post-merger. Yet, observing such an ejecta afterglow would provide constraints on the ejecta mass and velocity, *independent of optical/IR observations of the kilonova emission itself*. Since kilonova emission can be powered by a variety of sources beyond just r-process nucleosynthesis (e.g. wind from a magnetar remnant), inferences of the r-process yield in the ejecta from optical/IR observations can be biased. Additional constraints on the ejecta mass and velocity based on observations of the kilonova radio afterglow can aid in revealing the nature of the kilonova and its nucleosynthetic yield.

- Can we improve measurements of the Hubble constant? Detections of the synchrotron afterglow from off-axis sGRBs associated with DNS mergers can measure H_0 using gravitational waves (GWs) as standard sirens, since modelling of the GW waveforms provides a luminosity distance, and a multi-messenger detection of an EM counterpart can associate a host galaxy, hence redshift (Abbott et al., 2017a). However, this approach suffers from a distance-inclination degeneracy; since the GW emission from the merger is not isotropic, there is a degeneracy between the inferred distance and the orbital inclination. This degeneracy can be broken by detecting and monitoring the synchrotron afterglow of the associated sGRB because the light curve is sensitive to the jet axis angle (reasonably assuming that the jet is launched along the orbital axis). VLBI measurements of the superluminal motion of the jet can also constrain the jet axis angle for nearby sources (Mooley et al., 2018). For GW170817, the X-ray and radio afterglow light curves brightened and peaked at ~ 163 days post-merger before fading. A comparison to models showed that the jet was angled $20-25^\circ$ away from our line of sight. This breaks the degeneracy in calculations of H_0 based on GW170817, decreasing the uncertainty by a factor of $\sim 2-4$ (Hotokezaka et al., 2019). Radio observations are preferred because they provide denser and deeper sampling of the afterglow light curve compared to X-ray observations, which suffer from Sun constraint, and because VLBI observations are uniquely able to measure the jet’s superluminal motion.

5 Relevant New, Upcoming and Envisioned Radio Instruments

Here we describe new, upcoming and envisioned radio instruments of specific relevance to the science described in this white paper. Generally speaking, the needs of FRB science are complementary to those of slow transients. Though both demand high sensitivity and large baselines, the former requires very wide fields of view, and systematic long exposure sky monitoring at very large baselines but only very sparse uv coverage, while for the latter (with the exception of undirected searches for slow transients), small fields-of-view are sufficient for monitoring specific targets, but the more uv coverage, the better.

CHIME, the Canadian Hydrogen Intensity Mapping Experiment, is a recently commissioned transit telescope at DRAO in Penticton, sensitive in the 400–800 MHz band. Designed to map neutral hydrogen at intermediate redshifts in order to study (non-transient!) baryon acoustic oscillations, the daily mapping will also enable the regular study of bright slow transients. With angular resolution $\sim 30'$ and ~ 0.1 -mJy sensitivity (daily sensitivity in one $30'$ pixel), CHIME is useful for lightcurve modeling of bright transients, but not imaging. Hence CHIME will be useful for early-time observations of nearby sGRBs as well as for novel surveys for bright, slow transients.

CHIME/FRB is a realtime instrument that detects FRBs using 1024 FFT-beams that are searched at a 1-ms cadence. It is already detecting FRBs at unprecedented rates, by systematically monitoring the sky north of declination -11° with daily cadence and very long exposures near the celestial north pole. It is likely to detect several thousand FRBs in the next few years, which will enable significant progress on many of the aforementioned open FRB questions, including elucidating classes of sources, quantitative studies of repeatability, environment through RMs and scattering times, as well as realizing some cosmic probe applications via DM, SM and RM distributions and possibly lensing, and attempts at correlation with large scale structure. However the arc minute angular resolution provided by CHIME on its own does not permit identification of host galaxies.

CHIME/FRB Outriggers is a project in the planning stages to build smaller CHIME-like telescopes at ~ 1000 -km baselines to enable real-time VLBI triggered by CHIME/FRB detections. This will enable sub-arcsecond localizations of hundreds to thousands of events, hence host galaxy identifications and redshift determinations (given sufficient time on large optical telescopes – an issue). The measurement of hundreds of redshifts for FRBs unlocks the bulk of the potential for FRBs as cosmic probes, enabling quantitative studies of the locations of the missing baryons, studies of the structures of galaxy haloes, cosmology through the kSZ effect, on top of enabling detailed studies of FRB host galaxies and immediate environments. Though other FRB localization experiments are online (e.g. ASKAP, DSA-10) and/or planned (MeerKAT, DSA-110), CHIME/FRB outriggers will have by far the largest event rate and operates in a unique band (the rest being at 1.4 GHz). A detailed design study and construction of a prototype outrigger (to be built within ~ 100 km of Penticton) has been funded by the Gordon & Betty Moore Foundation. Site investigation for eventual distant outrigger sites is underway. CHIME/FRB outriggers would also be of great use for radio pulsar astrometry and scintillometry.

CHORD: (see white paper by Vanderlinde et al.) The Canadian Hydrogen Observatory and Radio-transient Detector (CHORD) is a proposed Candian-led next-generation radio telescope, with FRB science as a primary design driver. CHORD would consist of the CHIME/FRB “outrigger” stations which would work with CHIME/FRB to provide triggered sub-arcsecond localizations of hundreds to thousands of events, but complemented by a large core array of 512×6 -m dishes equipped with ultra-wideband detectors (300–1500 MHz), providing a much larger bandwidth and deeper view over a smaller area than CHIME. The deeper view would greatly increase the event rate, and offer novel insight into propagation effects. The CHORD outrigger stations feature both cylinders to match the CHIME/FRB field-of-view, and ultra-wide-band dishes to match the core array. Collectively, these allow CHORD to provide wide-band measurements and sub-arcsecond localization on dozens of events per day, tens of thousands over the course of its 5-year nominal observing run. CHORD will also be a powerful pulsar search machine (see white papers by Stairs et al. and Fonseca et al.).

JVLA is of great interest for all the aforementioned radio transients: FRBs for localizations of repeaters and deep studies of otherwise localized single-burst sources, slow transients for imaging and high-sensitivity monitoring, and the same for multi-messenger events. Moreover, VLASS is a treasure trove for time-domain astrophysics and novel transient identification.

SKA (see white paper by Spekkens et al.) The first phase of the SKA, SKA1, is divided into two instruments: SKA1-Low and SKA1-Mid. SKA1-Low operates in the 50–350 MHz band and consists of an array of 512 stations each with 256 antennas with a maximum baseline of 65 km, to be located in Australia. SKA1-Mid operates in different bands within the 350 MHz to at least 15 GHz MHz range and consists of 133 15-m dishes along with the 64 13.5-m dishes from MeerKAT, all located in South Africa with maximum baseline 150 km. The design of SKA2 is still under consideration. SKA1-Mid in particular will be very useful for slow transient monitoring with high sensitivity, useful for compact binaries and jet production as well as for the study of kilonova and ejecta in DNS mergers detected in GWs. SKA1 could be useful for follow-ups of FRBs to study in particular the luminosity function of repeaters and monitoring of variable continuum source emission as seen in FRB 121102, but too much

larger volumes. If FRBs are detectable in the SKA1-Low band, interesting propagation studies would be enabled. **ngVLA:** The next generation Very Large Array (ngVLA) is a forthcoming radio interferometer that is in development to be ~ 10 times more sensitive and possess ~ 10 times improved angular resolution than the JVLA and ALMA facilities (Murphy et al., 2018). Among the major science cases of the ngVLA is “slow” radio-transient astrophysics at high frequencies (i.e., 1.2-116 GHz). The ngVLA will further impact multi-messenger astronomy with greater constraints on energetics, structure and localization of radio counterparts to inspiraling DNS mergers detected by aLIGO/Virgo as described above. The ngVLA is also expected to probe details of the accretion physics and jet production in compact object binaries (e.g. Coppejans et al., 2018). The ngVLA would impact FRB science via studying the faint end of repeating source luminosity functions and monitoring of variable continuum radio source counterparts like that of FRB 121102 (Chatterjee et al., 2017) to much greater depth than is possible today. Though localization of repeating FRBs is a possibility, this would be more efficiently done by CHIME/FRB outriggers and/or CHORD.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

See science description above but in short, FRBs are a new and truly puzzling astrophysical phenomenon with potential to revolutionize studies of large-scale structure. Thus far they are exclusively observable at radio wavelengths. For slow transients, radio observations play an integral role in broad multi-wavelength studies, now sometimes including gravitational waves. The latter in particular is truly revolutionary.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

A risk in FRB science is not realizing their potential as cosmic probes by not having a large statistical sample with redshifts. This is mitigated by CHIME/Outriggers and CHORD. A risk with multi-messenger astrophysics is that observable DNS and NS/BH mergers are rare.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

CHIME and CHIME/FRB are Canadian led for all three items, as would be CHIME/Outriggers and CHORD. The JVLA has strong Canadian involvement in all three as well but is US-led. SKA is a broad international consortium in which Canada has an important voice in all items. Whether ngVLA will have significant Canadian leadership remains to be seen.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

By definition, radio transients fall in the radio domain. Nevertheless FRBs are of broad interest including to cosmologists and physicists interested in fundamental issues due to their promise as probes, and the optical community could be very helpful in following-up CHIME/Outriggers- and CHORD-localized FRBs. The Canadian time-domain astronomy community has broad interest and support for the slow radio transients science.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Leading in FRB science will position Canadians for future novel LSS studies and possibly novel cosmology

constraints. The continued development of gravitational wave detectors also promises that slow radio transient studies will be important in the next decade. The envisioned CHIME/Outriggers and CHORD projects will position Canadians for the future by training a generation of astronomers in seeing through a project from end-to-end including design, construction, commissioning, and science operations, as leaders.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

With CHIME and CHIME/FRB built and functional, operating them as a CHIME/Outrigger trigger telescope has a very favourable cost-benefit ratio.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

CHIME requires continued operations funding and there is no obvious source for this. Also, regarding FRB localization, if CHIME/Outriggers is successful, it will localize hundreds to thousands of FRBs, which then require us to get time on optical telescopes to identify host galaxies and obtain redshifts. Wide-field optical surveys will mitigate this somewhat.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

All of the above, but most notably industry opportunities in the development and construction of CHIME/Outriggers and CHORD. Additionally the latter offer particularly unique HQP training as described above.

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